

MORPHOLOGICAL CONTROL OF STRUCTURAL ELECTROLYTES FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

One of the key component for the implementation of energy storage capability into structural composite material is the dual-functional matrix that could simultaneously carry mechanical load and allow electrochemical reactions (structural batteries) or ionic conduction (structural capacitors), which could be referred to as structural electrolytes (SE) or multifunctional electrolytes (ME), within the device. In particular, the predominant class of SE/ME are the biphasic material with a continuous liquid electrolyte contained within solid skeletal structures. However, despite the numerous materials reported in the literature, there's an apparent paucity in the studies on the systematic control of the feature and pore sizes, as well as their relation to the overall performance of this class of materials. In the current study, two methods for the consistent control of feature and pore sizes by: i, the addition of a slow curing cycle; and ii, the introduction of a multifunctional block-co-polymer, on an epoxy and ionic liquid based formulation are demonstrated, together with their correlation to the performance of the material studied, the presented results may aid the tuning of future structural electrolyte materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

The potential of energy storage in carbon fibre based composites has recently been demonstrated and improvement of both the mechanical and electrochemical performances are still in progress [1]. One of the challenges for these multi-functional material is the development of an 'ideal' multifunctional matrix or structural electrolyte (SE) that could incorporate electrolytes with little compromise to the SE's structural performance. It has been demonstrated that a bi-continuous dual phase material, consisting of liquid electrolyte and solid structural cross-linked polymers, produced the most balanced performance between mechanical and electrochemical properties [2]. However, the correlation between the microstructure of the material has yet to be established, as a general and consistent method to control and tune the microstructure of this class of material remain elusive, which may provide an additional tool in their optimisations. Furthermore, the electrolyte channel size of these material are usually in the micron range, and were relatively difficult to control, which could lead to internal shorting by fibre penetration when carbon fibres are used as electrodes in structural super capacitors or dendrite formation in structural batteries [3]. It has been demonstrated recently that a bicontinuous SE with submicron channel size could be achieved by utilising poly(glycidyl methacrylate)-block-co-poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) and polyethylene glycol (200) as porogen [4]. However, the preparation of such material was relatively complex, requiring the use of a sacrificial polymer film, extraction of porogen, and subsequently refilling the membrane with liquid electrolytes, making this method only suitable as a mono-functional separator as bonding to the carbon fibre would be compromised [4]. In the current work, two methods for the consistent manipulation of morphology of a SE, consisted of the electrolyte 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (EMIM-TFSI) and the epoxy bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE) with the cross-linker isophoron diamine (IPDA) were explored: i, the introduction of a slow curing cycle, thus a more confined polymerisation induced phase separation (PIPS) process; and ii, the addition of a novel multi-functional block-co-polymer (MF-BcP) with a structural epoxy block and an ionic block, which serves as a templating agent with partial functionalities of the base SE with both

structural and ionic blocks, instead of the mono-function as porogens.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

BADGE and IPDA were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and was used as received unless otherwise stated. EMIM-TFSI was purchased from IoLitec and was used as received. All solvent used were purchased from Fisher Scientific and were used as received. The block-co-polymer, poly(glycidyl methacrylate)-block-poly[(2-dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate] butyl bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide] (pGMA-b-p(DMAEMA-TFSI, herein after referred to as MF-BcP) was synthesised according to reported method [5].

2.2 Structural electrolyte formulation

For the current study, two formulations of SE were used. SE1 consisted of 40 vol% of EMIM-TFSI, and SE2 in addition to 40 vol% of EMIM-TFSI contained 2.5 wt% (in relation to weight of SE1 of identical vol% EMIM-TFSI) of MF-BcP. The weight of each material for the two SEs consisted of 5 g of BADGE are listed in Table 1.

Sample	BADGE (g)	IPDA (g)	EMIM-TFSI (g)	MF-BcP (g)
SE1	5	1.2500	5.7455	0
SE2	5	1.2838	5.7455	0.2999

Table 1: Quantities of components for the formulations studied SEs.

2.2 Structural electrolyte preparation and curing

For SE1, BADGE was first melted at 50 °C and cooled to room temperature (RT) slowly to form a supercooled liquid. EMIM-TFSI was then added, followed by IPDA. The mixture was then stirred until a homogeneous liquid was achieved, and was degassed under vacuum. For the SE2, the pGMA-b-p(DMAEMA-TFSI) was first added to the supercooled BADGE, followed by EMIM-TFSI. The resulting mixture was then stirred until the polymer was fully solubilised, typically 5—7 days. IPDA was then added to the mixture followed by procedure described previously.

Two curing cycles were tested for the current study: **i**, 1 hour at 60 °C, 2 hours at 80 °C, and post cured at 120 °C for 2 hours; **ii**, as in **i** but with an additional 18—20 hours at RT curing prior to the described curing cycle. For SE1, both cycles were performed, and SE2 was cured with cycle **ii** only.

Samples of 50 mm × 80 mm × 2 mm were cured vertically in glass moulds coated with Chemlease™ 41-90 EZ, and were cut to required dimensions for subsequent characterisations.

2.3 Mechanical performance

Young's modulus of the cured materials was determined with 3-point bending test, conducted using the LR5KPlus advanced materials testing machine (Lloyd Instruments/Ametek). The anvil speeds were determined by:

$$v = \frac{\epsilon_{dot} l^2}{6h} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\varepsilon} = d\varepsilon/dt = 0.01 \text{ min}^{-1}$, l is the sample length (24 mm), and h is the sample height (2 mm). The Young's moduli of samples were then determined by:

$$E_b = \frac{l^3}{4wh^3} S \quad (2)$$

Where E_b is the Young's modulus (MPa), w is the width of the sample ($> 4 \text{ mm}$ or $2 \times h$), and S is the slope (N/mm) at the steepest ascend of the measurement. The average of a minimum of 5 samples for each SE and curing conditions are reported.

2.4 Ionic conductivity

The ionic conductivity was measured *via* impedance spectroscopy using a VersaSTAT 3-450 potentiostat. For each sample, two plaques of $50 \text{ mm} \times 12 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$ were cut from the top and bottom of the cured material described in Section 2.2, and were polished on each side facing the glass mould to remove the skin prior to the measurements. A thin layer of EMIM-TFSI was applied to the surface of the sample to minimise contact resistance. All measurements were taken at room temperature using a frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz with a sinusoidal voltage of amplitude 5 mV. The ionic conductivity of the sample was then determined by:

$$\sigma = L/AZ \quad (3)$$

where σ is the ionic conductivity (mS/cm), L is the distance between electrodes (sample thickness in cm) and A is the contact surface area (cm^2) and Z is the ionic impedance (Ω) determined by the intercept of the real Z axis using EIS spectrum analyser. For each sample, 5 areas on each plaque were measured, with the average of the 10 measurements per sample reported.

2.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy

The scanning electron microscopy was performed using the FEI Helios Nanolab 600, with accelerating voltages between 3.5 kV and 10 kV. The EMIM-TFSI was first removed by solvent exchange with ethanol (minimum 5 \times) and the ethanol was removed under vacuum. The samples were then freshly fractured and sputtered with a 5–20 nm layer of platinum (Cressington Coating System 328) prior to observation under SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology control

Firstly, the effect of slow curing cycle shall be discussed, the SEM observations of the SE1 cured with the two cycles are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Representative SEM images of SE1 cured under **A**, curing cycle i (2k magnification); and **B**, curing cycle ii (5k magnification).

As can be observed in Figure 1, both curing cycles produced bicontinuous morphologies. However, clear morphological changes can be seen with the addition of the slow curing cycle at RT. In particular, curing cycle **i** produced large, nodulous features (5—20 μm) that were fused to form a continuous epoxy skeletal network (Figure 1A). In contrast, when cured with cycle **ii**, the connected nodular domains were reduced significantly, along with a reduction in the structural skeletal size (2—4 μm). Furthermore, the said features appeared much more uniformly distributed when cured with cycle **ii** (Fig. 1B), lacking the large fused nodule features (*ca.* 20 μm) formed observed in materials cured with cycle **i** (Fig. 1A). Similar differences were also apparent when comparing the pore sizes and distributions between the two curing methods. These observations may suggest that the slower curing at RT led to the PIPS reaching a more confined local equilibrium, therefore, subsequent studies with the addition of SE2 was cured with cycle **ii** in an attempt to achieve the smallest features possible. The representative SEM images of SE2 cured with cycle **ii** are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Representative SEM images of SE2 at **A**, 5k; **B**, 50k; and **C** 200k magnifications.

As shown in Figure 2, the features observed from SE2 under comparable magnification (Figure 2A) of SE1 from both curing cycle (Figure 1) were significantly modified, and appeared to have lost the bicontinuous characteristics. Interestingly, when examined under higher magnification, a mixture of small, < 100 nm, and large, *ca.* 1 μm , nodulous and fibrous features (Fig. 2B) were apparent. Furthermore, the channels were successfully reduced to sub-micron scale, where nm scale bicontinuous morphology (down to 20 nm) could be clearly observed under 200k magnifications (Fig. 2C). These morphologies were likely achieved from the further confinement of the PIPS process through the templates formed by the addition of MF-BcP, as well as the potential effect on the polymerisation kinetics from the introduction of the epoxy containing polymer block.

3.2 Overall material performance with relation to morphologies

While the ability to control the materials' micron morphology essential, their general performance, namely the mechanical and electrochemical properties are of equal import. The key performance metrics, Young's moduli and ionic conductivities of the systems studied are listed in Table 2.

Formulation	Curing cycle	Young's modulus* (MPa)	Ionic conductivity* (mS/cm)	Mean feature/pore size (μm)
SE1	i	58 ± 0.1	2.42 ± 0.34	12.5
SE1	ii	289 ± 19	1.81 ± 0.10	3
SE2	ii	222 ± 14	1.58 ± 0.05	0.5

* Standard deviation of the sample population were reported as error for both Young's modulus and ionic conductivity.

Table 1: Mechanical and electrochemical properties of materials presented in the current study.

As shown in Table 2, the feature size of showed some interesting interdependence with the general performance of the materials studied. On the one hand, the ionic conductivity was reduced from 2.42 ± 0.34 mS/cm (*ca.* 12.5 μm) to 1.58 ± 0.05 mS/cm (*ca.* 0.5 μm). On the other hand, significant improvement (*ca.* 4 \times) of the mechanical properties were achieved when the skeletal length scale was reduced to below 5 μm but suffered slight degradation at sub-micron features. The observed trends are visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Mechanical and electrochemical performance of the material in relation to feature sizes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The works presented herein demonstrated two potential methods for the control of micro-morphologies of a dual phase structural electrolyte system. On the one hand, a slow curing cycle at RT achieved a moderate reduction in feature size, suggesting that the rate of curing may be a determinant for the phase separation process. On the other hand, the addition of MF-BvP was able to reduce the feature size by an order or magnitude to nm range. Furthermore, the feature size showed a clear effect on the general performance of the material, where the reduction to $< 5 \mu\text{m}$ resulted in a significant improvement of mechanical properties, but with a decrease in electrochemical performance. The morphological control methods and trends presented herein may therefore be used to help tune future multifunctional materials, and the universality of the presented work are currently under investigation.

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